

1 Anthropogenic chloroform emissions from 2 China drive changes in global emissions

3 *Minde An^{1,2,3}, Luke M. Western^{2,4}, Jianxin Hu^{1*}, Bo Yao^{5,6*}, Jens Mühle⁷, Anita L.*
4 *Ganesan⁸, Ronald G. Prinn³, Paul B. Krummel⁹, Ryan Hossaini¹⁰, Xuekun Fang¹¹,*
5 *Simon O'Doherty², Ray F. Weiss⁷, Dickon Young², Matthew Rigby^{2*}*

6 1 College of Environmental Sciences and Engineering, Peking University, Beijing,
7 China

8 2 School of Chemistry, University of Bristol, Bristol, UK

9 3 Center for Global Change Science, Massachusetts Institute of Technology, Cambridge,
10 MA, USA

11 4 Global Monitoring Laboratory, National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration,
12 Boulder, CO, USA

13 5 Department of Atmospheric and Oceanic Sciences & Institute of Atmospheric
14 Sciences, Fudan University, Shanghai, China

15 6 Meteorological Observation Centre of China Meteorological Administration
16 (MOC/CMA), Beijing, China

17 7 Scripps Institution of Oceanography, University of California San Diego, La Jolla,
18 CA, USA

19 8 School of Geographical Sciences, University of Bristol, Bristol, UK

20 9 Climate Science Centre, CSIRO Oceans and Atmosphere, Aspendale, Victoria,
21 Australia

22 10 Lancaster Environment Centre, Lancaster University, Lancaster, UK

23 11 College of Environmental & Resource Sciences, Zhejiang University, Zhejiang,
24 China

25 *** Corresponding authors:**

26 Jianxin Hu: jianxin@pku.edu.cn; Bo Yao: yaobo@fudan.edu.cn; Matthew Rigby:

27 Matt.Rigby@bristol.ac.uk

28

29 **Keywords:** chloroform; ozone layer depletion; Montreal Protocol; emissions; very
30 short-lived ozone-depleting substances

31 **Abstract**

32 Emissions of chloroform (CHCl_3), a short-lived halogenated substance not currently
33 controlled by the Montreal Protocol on Substances that Deplete the Ozone Layer, are
34 offsetting some of the achievements of the Montreal Protocol. In this study, emissions
35 of CHCl_3 from China were derived by atmospheric measurement-based “top-down”
36 inverse modelling and a sector-based “bottom-up” inventory method. Top-down CHCl_3
37 emissions grew from 88 (81-93) Gg yr^{-1} in 2011 to a maximum of 189 (172-205) Gg
38 yr^{-1} in 2017, followed by a decrease to 125 (118-132) Gg yr^{-1} in 2018, after which
39 emissions remained relatively constant through 2020. The changes in emissions from
40 China could explain nearly all the global changes during the study period. The CHCl_3
41 emissions in China were dominated by anthropogenic sources, such as by-product
42 emissions during disinfection and leakage from chloromethane industries. Had
43 emissions continued to grow at the rate observed up to 2017, a substantial delay in
44 ozone layer recovery would have occurred. However, this delay will be largely avoided
45 if global CHCl_3 emissions remain relatively constant in the future, as they have between
46 2018 and 2020.

47 **Introduction**

48 Due to the phase-down of production and consumption of long-lived ozone depleting
49 substances such as chlorofluorocarbons (CFCs), halons, and hydrochlorofluorocarbons
50 (HCFCs) under the Montreal Protocol on Substances that Deplete the Ozone layer, the
51 burden of stratospheric chlorine and bromine is declining and the Antarctic ozone hole
52 is showing signs of recovery^{1,2}. Previous studies have identified that halogenated very
53 short-lived substances (VSLS), defined as species with a total atmospheric lifetime
54 shorter than 6 months, play an increasing role in stratospheric ozone depletion^{3,4},
55 especially if they are emitted from regions with rapid transport pathways to the
56 stratosphere such as East and South Asia⁵⁻⁷. The impact of VSLS on ozone layer
57 depletion is more prominent if considered in terms of the integrated ozone depletion
58 (IOD)⁸ compared to the traditional metrics such as ozone depletion potential (ODP).

59 Chloroform (CHCl₃) is the second most abundant chlorine-containing VSLS, with a
60 lifetime of ~6 months¹. There was substantial growth in the measured global
61 atmospheric mole fractions of CHCl₃ and a rapid increase in global CHCl₃ emissions
62 between 2010-2015^{1,9}. If the growth of the atmospheric abundance of CHCl₃ were to
63 have continued at the rate observed between 2010 and 2015, it could delay stratospheric
64 ozone layer recovery by several years⁹, comparable to the impact from recent
65 unexpected CFC-11 emissions between 2013 and 2019^{10,11}. However, global CHCl₃
66 emissions and mole fractions have recently been found to have decreased after reaching
67 a maximum in 2017¹².

68 Given the growing impact of VSLs on ozone layer depletion compared to ozone
69 depleting substances controlled under the Montreal Protocol, it is important to better
70 understand the magnitude and distribution of their sources. The global increase in
71 CHCl_3 emissions between 2010 and 2015 was attributed primarily to anthropogenic
72 emissions in China⁹, but the contribution of individual source sectors was not
73 investigated in detail. Most of the CHCl_3 produced in China is thought to be consumed
74 as a feedstock and converted to HCFC-22¹³, where only a few percent of the feedstock
75 is thought to leak to the atmosphere^{14,15}. Several disinfection processes may lead to by-
76 product emissions of CHCl_3 via haloform reactions^{16,17}, but their contribution has not
77 been quantified. In addition to anthropogenic sources, natural sources of CHCl_3
78 including ocean emissions and terrestrial soil emissions are also significant worldwide
79 (accounting for more than 50% of the global emissions)¹⁷⁻²⁰ and may contribute
80 substantially to CHCl_3 emissions in China. To date, there has been no sector-based
81 bottom-up inventory for CHCl_3 emissions in China, and thus little quantitative
82 understanding of the potential source sectors responsible for the increase in CHCl_3
83 emissions. The cause of the global emission decrease after 2017 has not previously been
84 identified.

85 Quantifying CHCl_3 emissions from China is important considering its predominant role
86 in the global increase between 2010-2015⁹ and the rapid upward transport to the
87 stratosphere of emissions from East Asia compared to those from other industrialized
88 areas such as mid-latitude Europe or North America^{6,7}. In this study, we provide a time-
89 series of CHCl_3 emissions from China (defined as the Chinese mainland, excluding

90 Hong Kong, Macao and ocean areas) using sector-based “bottom-up” information
91 (2006-2020) and atmospheric measurement-based “top-down” methods (2011-2020),
92 to constrain CHCl₃ emissions and examine the potential sources driving the apparent
93 trends. Previous top-down emissions estimates were localized to eastern China and
94 were derived from measurements of atmospheric mole fractions made outside of China⁹,
95 while the top-down estimation in this study focuses on emissions from the whole of
96 China, derived from long-term measurements from a network of nine sites within China.
97 The results in this study combined with previously reported global emissions allow a
98 better understanding of global-scale changes in emissions of CHCl₃ and their potential
99 impact on the ozone layer.

100 **Methods**

101 **Site description and measurement**

102 The regional top-down inversion of CHCl₃ emissions from China used measurements
103 at nine sites from the China Meteorological Administration (CMA): Akedala (AKD,
104 47.10° N 87.97° E), Lin’an (LAN, 30.30° N 119.73° E), Longfengshan (LFS, 44.73° N
105 127.60° E), Jiangjin (JGJ, 29.15° N 106.15° E), Jinsha (JSA, 29.64° N 114.21° E),
106 Shangdianzi (SDZ, 40.65° N 117.21° E), Mt. Waliguan (WLG, 36.29° N 100.90° E),
107 Shangri-La (XGL, 28.01° N 99.44° E), and Xinfeng (XFG, 24.08° N 114.17° E). These
108 sites provide measurements with sensitivity to emissions sources across China
109 (Supplementary Fig. S1). All the sites are far (typically 10s to 100s of km) from heavily
110 industrialized areas, thus minimizing the influence of very localized emissions sources

111 on the measurements. A summary of the sampling period and frequency at each site is
112 provided in Supplementary Table S1. Ambient air samples were collected weekly in
113 flasks at AKD, LFS, JSA, SDZ, WLG, XGL and XFG, and daily from JGJ. At LAN,
114 the sampling frequency was weekly before 2019 and daily thereafter. All flask air
115 samples were sent to the CMA Beijing lab for analysis. In addition to the flask
116 samplings above, there were also high-frequency in-situ measurements at SDZ during
117 the study period. More detailed information about the measurement sites and sampling
118 processes are provided in previous papers²¹⁻²³.

119 Two instruments were used in this study to analyze the mole fractions of CHCl_3 in the
120 air samples: an AGAGE ‘Medusa’ gas chromatographic system with mass
121 spectrometric detector (GC/MS)^{24,25}, and a 2-channel gas chromatograph with electron-
122 capture detector (GC-ECD)²⁶. All the flask samples were analyzed by the GC/MS
123 system at CMA. At SDZ, ambient air was sampled and analyzed every 2 hours by the
124 GC/MS system and every 80 minutes by the GC-ECD system. Every air sample was
125 bracketed by an analysis of the working standard to calibrate the drift in the system. All
126 CHCl_3 measurements are reported on the SIO-98 calibration scale²⁷. Measurement
127 precisions were estimated at 3.4%, 0.6% and 1.5% for the in-situ GC-ECD, in-situ
128 GC/MS at SDZ and flask samples, respectively. If both GC/MS and GC-ECD SDZ in-
129 situ measurements were available in a specific year, the measurements using GC/MS
130 were used in the inversion unless the GC/MS instrument was not operational in that
131 year, in which case the GC-ECD measurements were used. All in-situ measurements
132 from SDZ were averaged over a period of 24 hours in the inversion framework. In

133 addition, a “local influence” filter was applied to the daily samples at JGJ, LAN and in-
134 situ measurements at SDZ to remove measurements where the signal is mostly
135 influenced by emissions sources close to the sites (if they exist), which are poorly
136 represented in the inversion framework. We filtered out observations where more than
137 10% of the measurement sensitivity to emissions comes from the 25 grid cells
138 surrounding the measurement site in the atmospheric transport model (see next section).
139 After re-sampling and filtering, a total of 4030 processed measurements were included
140 in the inversions to estimate emissions from China.

141 **Regional inversion framework**

142 To derive emissions, the observations from the CMA network were combined with
143 sensitivities of each measurement to the emissions from each grid within a regional
144 domain. Sensitivities to emissions were modelled using the UK Met Office Numerical
145 Atmospheric-dispersion Modelling Environment (NAME)²⁸, a Lagrangian Particle
146 Dispersion Model. A detailed description of the inversion framework can be found in
147 previously published papers^{21,29}. Here we provide a brief overview and updates.

148 The domain in which sensitivities to emissions were calculated was bounded at 5° S,
149 74° N and 55° E, 192° E. In the NAME model run, tracer particles were released at a
150 rate of 20,000 per hour from the sampling location within a ± 10 m vertical window and
151 the model was run backwards in time for 30 days (or until the particles left the
152 computational domain). NAME is driven by meteorological fields from the UK Met
153 Office Unified Model³⁰. Particles in the lowest 40 m of the atmosphere were regarded

154 as having interacted with surface emissions, and sensitivities were integrated over the
155 30-day simulations³¹. Chemical loss during transport was not considered, as a previous
156 study showed that the chemical loss plays only a minor role in the regional inversion
157 for CHCl₃ (<1% of the derived emissions, which is small compared to other estimated
158 uncertainties in the inversion)⁹.

159 The emissions of CHCl₃ from China were solved by a hierarchical Bayesian inference
160 framework^{21,31,32}. The emissions and the model-measurement uncertainties were
161 sampled by a Markov Chain Monte-Carlo (MCMC) method, constructed by a No-U-
162 Turn sampler³³ and a slice sampler³⁴. The MCMC chain used 2.5×10^5 steps, and the first
163 5×10^4 steps from the chain were discarded. Prior to sampling, 1.25×10^5 tuning steps
164 were run. The mean and 68% uncertainty interval from the posterior distribution were
165 calculated as the reported emissions and their uncertainties. In the Bayesian inference,
166 the a priori estimate for emissions of CHCl₃ from China was 50 Gg yr⁻¹ throughout the
167 period, which was distributed in space by a function of nightlight density data from
168 NOAA DMSP-OLS (Defense Meteorological Satellite Program-Operational Line-Scan
169 System, https://ngdc.noaa.gov/eog/data/web_data/v4composites/), where nightlight
170 values below 0.5 were treated as zero. A total of 10 Gg yr⁻¹ (20%) of the a priori
171 emissions were allocated uniformly to the grids with zero nightlight values to simulate
172 the natural sources. The a priori estimate for mole fractions at the domain boundaries
173 come from the 3D TOMCAT model³⁵.

174 The parameters estimated in the inversion were scaling factors to the a priori emissions

175 across 150 regions in the domain, scaling factors to the boundary conditions on each
176 horizontal boundary and the model error. These were solved for on an annual resolution.
177 The scaling factors for the a priori emissions and a priori boundary conditions were
178 sampled from a log-normal prior distribution with mean and standard deviation of 1,
179 which can constrain the posteriori values to an appropriate magnitude. Inversions using
180 a truncated-normal distribution (mean of 1, standard deviation of 10, bounded at 0)
181 were also performed to test the robustness of the results, which shows great consistency
182 with the log-normal distribution (Supplementary Fig. S2).

183 **Bottom-up inventory for CHCl₃ in China**

184 The bottom-up inventory considers both anthropogenic sources and natural sources for
185 CHCl₃ emissions in China. The categories (source sectors) of anthropogenic emissions
186 in the inventory are shown in Fig. 1. Anthropogenic emissions of CHCl₃ in China
187 mainly originate from emissions or leakages during intentional consumption or
188 production of CHCl₃ (defined as intended emissions in this study), and unintended
189 emissions of CHCl₃ during processes where CHCl₃ is emitted as an unwanted by-
190 product (defined as by-product emissions in this study). The intended emissions include
191 emissions from (a) production leakage, (b) feedstock use leakage and (c) solvent use in
192 the pharmaceutical industry. The by-product emissions sector is a considerable source
193 of CHCl₃ emissions, where CHCl₃ may be formed as a disinfectant by-product through
194 a haloform reaction, be produced during combustion or in anaerobic processes
195 associated with methane^{16,17}. In this study, the by-product sector includes (d) the pulp

196 and paper industry, (e-g) water treatment, (h) biomass burning, (i) coal combustion, (j)
 197 waste incineration, (k) landfill, and (l) livestock.

198

199 **Fig. 1 Categories of source sectors for anthropogenic CHCl₃ emissions in China**
 200 **considered in the bottom-up inventory.** The anthropogenic emissions include two
 201 categories, intended emissions (sector a-c), which are the emissions or leakages of
 202 CHCl₃ during its intentional consumption or production, and by-product emissions
 203 (sector d-l), which are the emissions of CHCl₃ as an unwanted by-product in some
 204 processes. The details for each sector can be found in the Methods. The natural
 205 emissions, sector (m), are not shown in this diagram.

206 The emissions in each sector, unless specified otherwise, were estimated by multiplying
 207 activity data for each sector by the corresponding emission factors, as shown by
 208 equation (1),

209
$$E_i = Ef_i \times A_i \tag{1}$$

210 where E_i is the emission of CHCl_3 in sector i in a specific year; Ef_i is the emission
211 factor(s) in that sector; and A_i is the corresponding activity data in the sector. All
212 activity data and emission factors are listed in Supplementary Table S2-4.

213 The total CHCl_3 production data in 2006-2010 and 2013-2020 were taken from the
214 China Chlor-Alkali Industry Association (CCAIA)¹³. CCAIA also provides total
215 chloromethane production data in 2006-2020¹³. There is no data on CHCl_3 production
216 in 2011-2012 and so these data were estimated by multiplying the total chloromethane
217 production in 2011/2012, obtained from CCAIA¹³, by the percentage of CHCl_3
218 production to total chloromethane production, averaged over the year before and after
219 the missing data (i.e., 2010 and 2013). The import and export data were taken from
220 China Customs Statistics Yearbook or CCAIA^{13,36}. The consumption data were
221 calculated as production plus import minus export.

222 For production leakage, sector (a), we applied 0.5-4% as a range of leakage rates in this
223 study to account for the uncertainties in emissions during production or other relevant
224 processes such as fugitive emissions during transport and storage. The 0.5% leakage
225 rate is recommended by IPCC 2000 guidelines³⁷ for substitutes of ozone depleting
226 substances and 4% is recommended by IPCC 2019 guidelines³⁸ for fluorochemicals.

227 For sector (b), all feedstock use of CHCl_3 in China is for production of HCFC-22, which
228 may be used directly or further used as feedstock for fluorinated polymers. In this sector,
229 the amount of CHCl_3 used for HCFC-22 production was derived from annual HCFC-
230 22 production³⁹ and mass balance of CHCl_3 to HCFC-22 conversion, with a conversion

231 efficiency of 95 % (following consultation with industry experts; this value is similar
232 to values previously reported for production of HFC-32¹⁵). We assumed 0.5% as the
233 leakage rate during feedstock use for HCFC-22 production, similar to leakage rates
234 during feedstock use reported in previous studies^{14,15,21}.

235 For sector (c), the majority of CHCl₃ used in other industrial processes, except for its
236 feedstock use for HCFC-22 production, is as a solvent in the pharmaceutical
237 industry^{13,16}. Thus, in this study, the CHCl₃ emissions from other industrial processes
238 only refer to emissions during solvent use in pharmaceutical manufacturing. About 8-
239 10% of CHCl₃ consumption was used as a solvent in the pharmaceutical industry¹³,
240 which is adopted as the activity data in this sector (c). We assumed an emission factor
241 of 5-16% in sector (c)^{16,21,40}.

242 In the pulp and paper industry, sector (d), CHCl₃ could be produced as a by-product
243 during disinfecting or bleaching processes. The activity data for sector (d) was the paper
244 produced each year in China, taken from the China Statistical Yearbook⁴¹, and the
245 emission factors were 5.3×10^{-5} to 4.54×10^{-4} g CHCl₃ per gram of paper produced^{16,20,40}.

246 The water treatment sector emits CHCl₃ during disinfection in drinking water treatment
247 (sector (e)), wastewater treatment (sector (f)), and other water treatment (sector (g)).

248 The amount of drinking water and wastewater treated each year was obtained from the
249 China Urban-Rural Construction Statistical Yearbook⁴² and used as the activity data in
250 these sectors. The emission factors were 4.1×10^{-5} and 1.4×10^{-5} g L⁻¹ for drinking water
251 treatment and wastewater treatment, respectively⁴⁰. The emissions from other water

252 treatment were estimated to be 70 % of the sum of emissions from drinking water
253 treatment and wastewater treatment¹⁶.

254 For sector (h), the emissions of CHCl₃ from biomass burning were estimated by the
255 emission ratio of CHCl₃/CO and CHCl₃/CO₂⁴³. The reference emissions of CO and CO₂
256 from biomass burning were obtained from a previous study⁴⁴, where the emissions of
257 the two substances after 2015 were extrapolated linearly from the data in 2008-2014.
258 The average of the two derived emissions based on CO and CO₂, respectively, in each
259 year was adopted as the emissions of CHCl₃ from biomass burning.

260 For sector (i), the amount of coal combusted was obtained from the China Energy
261 Statistical Yearbook⁴⁵, and the emission factor of CHCl₃ from coal combustion was
262 2.95×10^{-8} g CHCl₃ per gram of coal burned⁴⁶.

263 For sector (j) and (k), the quantity of waste incineration and waste landfill were obtained
264 from the China Urban-Rural Construction Statistical Yearbook⁴², used as the activity
265 data in the sectors, and the emission factors for the two sectors were 3.51×10^{-8} to 5.39
266 $\times 10^{-7}$ g CHCl₃ per gram of waste incinerated (obtained from USEPA⁴⁶), and 6.33×10^{-7}
267 g CHCl₃ per gram of landfill (averaged from Liu et al. ⁴⁷), respectively.

268 For sector (l), the emissions of CHCl₃ from livestock were estimated by the emissions
269 of CH₄ from livestock averaged from different studies⁴⁸⁻⁵⁰, and the emission ratio of 2
270 $\times 10^{-5}$ g CHCl₃ per gram of CH₄ produced^{16,17}. The emissions of CH₄ from Chang et al.⁵⁰
271 in 2019-2020 were extrapolated linearly by available data in all other years.

272 Natural sources contribute to ~50-90% of the global CHCl₃ emissions reported in
273 previous studies¹⁷⁻²⁰. For the natural CHCl₃ emissions in China, the sector (m), only
274 terrestrial natural emissions are considered as there is no ocean area involved for China
275 in this study. The terrestrial natural emissions of CHCl₃ include emissions from several
276 land types such as peatland emissions⁵¹, forest soil emissions⁵² or rice field emissions⁵³
277 (rice emissions are anthropogenic but categorized into terrestrial natural emissions in
278 this study for ease of calculation), and the real release rate of CHCl₃ over different
279 terrestrial land types may be highly variable^{17,52,53}. Here, we used a range of CHCl₃
280 release rate from soil of 4-13 μg m⁻² d⁻¹ measured by a reported chamber study⁵⁴, which
281 lies within the same magnitudes as several field studies¹⁷, to approximately calculate
282 the CHCl₃ emissions from soil processes in China, based on a land area of ~ 9.6 × 10¹²
283 m². These estimated soil emissions give a representation of the terrestrial CHCl₃
284 emissions in China.

285 All the statistical data obtained directly from the statistical yearbooks and reference
286 emissions obtained from other studies, which were used to quantify the activity data in
287 each sector, were assumed to have a normal distribution with 5 % uncertainty. If
288 multiple values or a value range was given for a specific variable, a uniform distribution
289 would be adopted to calculate the uncertainty. A Monte Carlo method with 10,000
290 samples was used to estimate the emissions and their uncertainties (68% interval).

291 **Integrated ozone depletion**

292 Integrated ozone depletion (IOD) is a metric that estimates the time-integrated column

293 ozone depletion caused by new emissions of ozone depleting substances⁸. Compared to
294 the ‘delay in ozone return’ metric, IOD is more appropriate for short-lived species, as
295 it can reflect their contribution to ozone depletion in the short term, even if there is little
296 change in the ozone layer recovery date. The IOD can be estimated by the atmospheric
297 lifetime and total halogen emissions of a gas⁸. Pyle et al.⁸ provided the IOD from an
298 annual averaged 300 Gg yr⁻¹ increase in CH₂Cl₂ emissions between 2007-2017 (a
299 period of 11 years) of about 55 DU years. Considering that CHCl₃ has a similar lifetime
300 to CH₂Cl₂ (both ~180 days), we assume that the IOD of CHCl₃ can be simply scaled
301 based on its total chlorine emission. Therefore we estimate that the global chlorine
302 emissions from CHCl₃ increased roughly by an annual average of 40 Gg yr⁻¹ during
303 2011-2020 (derived from global CHCl₃ emissions reported in Laube and Tegtmeier et
304 al., 2022)¹². Thus, accounting for the mass difference of chlorine between CH₂Cl₂ and
305 CHCl₃, the IOD from increased CHCl₃ emissions over 10 years (2011-2020) is
306 approximately 8 DU years, which is comparable to that of the unexpected emissions of
307 CFC-11 since 2012 (~ 9-34 DU years)⁸.

308 **Results**

309 **Top-down emissions of CHCl₃ in China and contribution to global emissions**

310 Emissions of CHCl₃ in China during 2011-2020 were derived from measurements of
311 atmospheric mole fraction from nine sites within China (see Methods, measurement
312 data shown in Supplementary Fig. S3 and Supplementary Data file 1). Figure 2a shows
313 that emissions in China increased from 88 (81-93) Gg yr⁻¹ in 2011 to 189 (172-205) Gg

314 yr⁻¹ in 2017, continuing the increase in CHCl₃ emissions from eastern China previously
 315 reported through 2015⁹, although in 2016 emissions were lower than in 2015 (which
 316 will be discussed in the following bottom-up emissions section and discussion section).
 317 A decrease in CHCl₃ emissions occurred after the maximum in 2017, reaching 125
 318 (118-132) Gg yr⁻¹ in 2018. Emissions were approximately constant during 2018-2020.
 319 The derived emissions and their trends are generally insensitive to a priori assumptions,
 320 such as the magnitude and spatial distribution of the prior emissions, the choice of
 321 probability distribution in the Bayesian inversion framework (Supplementary Fig. S2),
 322 the choice of Chinese measurement sites used, or different methods of filtering the data
 323 (Supplementary Fig. S4).

324

325 **Fig. 2 Annual CHCl₃ emissions in China and global emissions.** (A) A comparison of
 326 CHCl₃ emissions in China with global emissions. The annual emissions in China can
 327 be found in Supplementary Data file 2. The annual global emissions are derived from
 328 Laube and Tegtmeier et al. (2022)¹². (B) The increase in the global emissions and
 329 emissions in China between 2011 and 2017 (i.e., 2017 minus 2011) and the decrease

330 *between 2017 and 2020 (i.e., 2017 minus 2020). The uncertainties, indicated by shading*
331 *in (A) and error bars in (B) are 1-sigma or the 68% uncertainty interval.*

332 The derived top-down emissions from China play an important role in the global
333 emissions, accounting for ~30-50% of the global total over 2011-2020, with a
334 maximum proportion of the global total of ~50% in 2017 (Fig. 2a). The emissions in
335 China show a similar trend to the global emissions, which both reached a maximum in
336 2017, followed by a decrease and then a plateau between 2018 and 2020. The pre-2017
337 increase (difference between the years 2011 and 2017) and the post-2017 decrease
338 (difference between the years 2017 and 2020) of emissions in China are of the same
339 magnitude, or even larger, than the global change in the same period (Fig. 2b). These
340 coincident emission trends indicate that the changes of CHCl₃ emissions from China
341 may be the dominant contributor to global emission changes during this period.

342 Anthropogenic emission sources are indicated to be the dominant driver for the
343 emission changes globally and in China, as it is not possible to explain the entire
344 variation in global emissions by changes from terrestrial natural sources over the land
345 area of China alone (see following section). The global annual mean mole fractions of
346 CHCl₃ also show a similar trend to global emissions and emissions in China (Fig. 3,
347 derived from Laube and Tegtmeier et al. (2022)¹²), i.e., increasing through 2017 and
348 then decreasing. The variation in the Northern Hemispheric mean mole fraction has
349 largely mirrored that of the global mean, while the mole fractions in the Southern
350 Hemisphere have been comparably stable since 2011. Given the short atmospheric

351 lifetime of CHCl_3 , it also indicates the dominant role of Northern Hemisphere
352 anthropogenic emissions in the changes of global CHCl_3 , which supports our finding.

353

354 **Fig. 3 Global mole fractions of CHCl_3 .** (A) Global-averaged annual mean mole
355 fractions of CHCl_3 . The annual mean values are plotted at the beginning of each year.
356 (B) Zonally averaged semi-hemispheric monthly mean mole fractions of CHCl_3 . (C)
357 Growth rate of the semi-hemispheric monthly mean mole fractions of CHCl_3 . The ticks
358 on the x-axis refer to the beginning of each year. All presented data were derived from
359 Laube and Tegtmeier et al. (2022)¹². Uncertainties, indicated by shading, are the 68%
360 interval (~ 1 -sigma).

361 **Bottom-up CHCl_3 emissions in China and source identification**

362 To understand the source sectors that drive the changes in CHCl_3 emissions in China, a
363 process-based bottom-up inventory for CHCl_3 emissions in China was compiled for the

364 first time using up-to-date data representative of applications which release CHCl_3 . The
 365 bottom-up inventory considers both anthropogenic sources and natural sources (see
 366 Methods for details). The anthropogenic emission source sectors are listed in Fig. 1,
 367 which includes intended anthropogenic emissions and by-product anthropogenic
 368 emissions. The bottom-up inventory emissions (Fig. 4) show an increasing trend over
 369 2011-2019, from 72 (58-86) Gg yr^{-1} in 2006 to 110 (87-131) Gg yr^{-1} in 2019, then a
 370 decrease to 104 (84-126) Gg yr^{-1} in 2020. The bottom-up emissions in this study are
 371 higher than previously derived emissions using an inter-species correlation method<sup>55-
 372 57</sup>, although emissions derived using inter-species correlation can be highly uncertain
 373 (Fig. 4a). The bottom-up emissions are also higher than a previous top-down CHCl_3
 374 emissions from eastern China between 2010 and 2015⁹, suggesting substantial
 375 emissions outside of the eastern China region. Our bottom-up emissions agree well with
 376 a previous top-down emissions estimate for China in 2007²⁶ (Fig. 4a).

377

378 **Fig. 4 Bottom-up and top-down CHCl_3 emissions in China.** (A) A comparison of the
 379 top-down and bottom-up emissions in China derived in this study and from previous
 380 studies. The previous results include Fang et al.⁹, Li et al.⁵⁵, Wang et al.⁵⁶, Kim et al.⁵⁷
 381 and Vollmer et al.²⁶. The results from Fang et al.⁹ only include CHCl_3 emissions from

382 *eastern China. ISC means emissions derived using an inter-species correlation method.*

383 **(B)** *Stacked sectoral emissions of the bottom-up results. The definition for each*
384 *category can be found in the Methods. Sectoral emissions with uncertainties are shown*
385 *in Supplementary Data file 3.*

386 Anthropogenic sources dominate the CHCl₃ emissions in China (Fig. 4b), accounting
387 for ~68% of the overall emissions (averaged throughout the period). The largest
388 anthropogenic source is by-product emissions of CHCl₃ from the pulp and paper sector,
389 contributing ~20-35% to total bottom-up emissions, where CHCl₃ can be released
390 during disinfecting or bleaching via haloform reaction when using chlorine-containing
391 bleach^{16,17}. The important role of the pulp and paper sector for CHCl₃ emissions is
392 consistent with the conclusion from a previous global inventory¹⁶. This sector also
393 contributed substantially to the increase during 2006-2019 in the bottom-up inventory,
394 accounting for ~38% of the emissions increase. Production leakage is the second largest
395 anthropogenic source, contributing ~10-25% to the overall emissions. This includes
396 CHCl₃ emissions from several production-related processes such as CHCl₃ production,
397 transport and storage. The production leakage sector contributes most to the increase
398 during 2006-2019 (~40%) and decrease during 2019-2020 (~87%) in the bottom-up
399 inventory. The variation in CHCl₃ emissions from production leakage is driven by the
400 rapid increase and decrease in CHCl₃ production in China (CHCl₃ production in China
401 is shown in Supplementary Fig. S5), because a constant emission factor for production
402 leakage was used throughout. The solvent use of CHCl₃ in the pharmaceutical industry
403 also contributes substantially to overall bottom-up emissions (~5-10%), to the 2006-

404 2019 emission increase (~12%) and the 2019-2020 decrease (~36%).

405 In addition to the anthropogenic emissions, previous studies reported relatively
406 uncertain but substantial contributions of natural sources to global CHCl₃ emissions,
407 ranging from ~50% to 90%¹⁷⁻²⁰, where terrestrial and ocean sources are thought to be
408 of similar magnitude^{17,18}. In this study, the derived CHCl₃ emissions from natural soil
409 sources (representing the terrestrial emissions) account for ~32% (averaged throughout
410 the period) of the bottom-up emissions in China (Fig. 4b). As we only consider
411 emissions from land, no oceanic emissions of CHCl₃ in China are included.

412 The bottom-up emissions estimates in this study account for ~60-100% of the top-down
413 emissions estimates. There are substantial discrepancies between the top-down and
414 bottom-up emissions in 2015 and 2017. The large year-to-year variation in the top-
415 down emission estimates, including the temporary decrease in 2016 and the post-2017
416 decrease (Fig. 4a), are also not well explained by the bottom-up emission estimates.
417 The mismatch may be caused by many of the unknowns (like the potential emissions
418 from the chlor-alkali industry discussed in the next section) or uncertainties in the
419 bottom-up inventory due to the limitation in the availability of activity data or emission
420 factors in several sectors.

421 The reported uncertainties in the bottom-up inventory are large enough that they could
422 encapsulate some of the year-to-year variability seen in the top-down estimates. Most
423 of the uncertainties in the inventory come from production leakage, the pulp and paper
424 industry, solvent use in pharmaceutical industry and natural soil sources

425 (Supplementary Data file 3). The bottom-up inventory does not explicitly include time-
426 varying emissions factors, e.g., a constant range of emission factors was used
427 throughout the period for production leakage (0.5-4%) and pulp and paper industry
428 (5.3×10^{-5} - 4.54×10^{-4} g/g paper). However, year-to-year changes in these factors are
429 possible. For example, a decrease in the emission factors in the pulp and paper industry
430 (in terms of emissions per gram of paper) may result from increasing use of chlorine-
431 free bleach^{58,59}, and a possible decrease in emission factors for production leakage may
432 be due to actions to control pollutants from factories (e.g. ref.⁶⁰ which came into force
433 in 2017) in order to meet the 2017 target of the Air Pollution Prevention and Control
434 Action Plan in China⁶¹. If the entire uncertainty range of the production leakage rate
435 from the IPCC 2019 guidelines³⁸ was considered (see Supplementary Fig. S6 for
436 details), the year-to-year variation in the top-down estimates could be explained by
437 uncertainties in the bottom-up estimates. Further potential changes could be due to a
438 sharp decrease in the volume of pharmaceutical production in China after 2017 (see
439 Supplementary Fig. S5 for details)⁴¹, where CHCl_3 is used as a solvent during
440 pharmaceutical manufacturing.

441 In addition to potential unaccounted-for changes in anthropogenic emissions, it is
442 possible that our bottom-up model has not accounted for substantial changes in natural
443 emissions, as no time-varying and land type-dependent emissions factors were included.
444 A negative correlation between the top-down emissions in China and annual average
445 precipitation⁶², especially after 2015 (Pearson Correlation Coefficient 'r' is -0.74,
446 $p < 0.001$ for ANOVA), and a positive correlation for the annual average temperature⁶²

447 and the emissions ($r=0.68$, $p<0.001$ for ANOVA), were identified (Supplementary Fig.
448 S7). Extreme rainfall events in China in 2016⁶² may be part of the explanation for the
449 low emissions in 2016, as flooded conditions could sharply reduce CHCl_3 emission
450 rates from soil⁶³. High temperatures also have the potential to enhance the release of
451 CHCl_3 ⁶⁴. However, considering that natural emissions are spread over terrestrial and
452 ocean areas across the world, the changes in natural emissions from China cannot
453 explain the entire global change, and are unlikely to be the main cause for the year-to-
454 year variation.

455 **Spatial distribution of CHCl_3 emissions in China and source identification**

456 From examination of the spatial distribution of CHCl_3 emissions in China derived from
457 atmospheric observations (shown in Fig. 5), most of the emission hotspots are in
458 northern and eastern China. Provincial and regional emissions for each year are
459 provided in Supplementary Data file 2 and Supplementary Fig. S8, respectively. North
460 and East China (the definitions for each region can be found in Supplementary Fig. S8),
461 including Hebei, Inner Mongolia, Shandong and Jiangsu provinces, have high
462 emissions compared to other regions throughout the study period. These regions are
463 also among the highest contributors to the pre-2017 emissions increase and post-2017
464 decrease (Fig. 5e-f). North and East China are highly economically developed and
465 industrialized regions, indicating the dominant role of anthropogenic sources in CHCl_3
466 emissions in China.

467

468 **Fig. 5** Spatial distributions of CHCl_3 emissions in China. (A) The mean posterior
 469 emissions over 2011-2015. (B) The mean posterior emissions in 2016. (C) The mean
 470 posterior emissions in 2017. (D) The mean posterior emissions over 2018-2020. € The
 471 difference in spatial distribution between 2017 and the 2011-2016 average (i.e., 2017
 472 minus the average of 2011-2016). (F) The difference in spatial distribution between the
 473 2018-2020 average and 2017 (i.e., the average of 2018-2020 minus 2017). The time
 474 periods are divided to show the period before and after the maximum emissions year in
 475 2017 (pre-2017 increase and post-2017 decrease). The spatial distributions of the mean
 476 posterior emissions in each individual year are shown in Supplementary Fig. S9. The

477 *quantitative provincial and regional emissions for each year are provided in*
478 *Supplementary Data file 2. The black dots in the figures are the measurement sites*
479 *active in the period. The pink triangles are the known chloromethane factories in China,*
480 *some of which are also the main fluorine chemical factories in China producing HCFC-*
481 *22 (where CHCl_3 is used as a feedstock).*

482 The locations of some regions with high emissions are consistent with the locations of
483 major chloromethane factories (mainly located in Shandong Province (in East China),
484 the Yangtze River Delta region (in East China) and the Sichuan Basin (approximately
485 at 103-108° E, 28-32° N), see Fig. 5), where fugitive emissions of chloromethanes have
486 previously been identified^{65,66}. Significant leakage of CHCl_3 from chloromethane
487 factories during processes such as production, storage, or transport, identified by the
488 bottom-up inventory in this study, are thus a likely source of emissions. The existence
489 of high emissions in the Sichuan Basin region surrounding the Jiangjin (JGJ) site since
490 2017 also indicates the potential for emissions from chloromethanes factories (see
491 Supplementary Fig. 9-10 for details), while the decrease in emissions in the Sichuan
492 Basin during 2017-2020 (Fig. 5f) may be evidence for a decrease in the emission factor
493 for production leakage from chloromethane factories.

494 There are similar spatial distribution patterns between CHCl_3 emissions (Fig. 5) and the
495 pulp and paper industry and the pharmaceutical industry (Supplementary Fig. 11a-b).

496 There are no chloromethane factories in Hebei province (in North China), although the
497 emissions in Hebei are substantial, especially in 2015-2016 and 2018-2020 when Hebei

498 is the province with the largest emissions. Hebei is one of the most industrialized
499 provinces in China where there is substantial pulp and paper production and
500 pharmaceutical production. High CHCl_3 emissions and large paper and pharmaceutical
501 production are also co-located in Shandong and Jiangsu provinces (in Yangtze River
502 Delta region) in East China.

503 There are substantial CHCl_3 emissions from Inner Mongolia (in North China) and
504 Xinjiang (in Northwest China) provinces (Fig. 5), which are not highly populated or
505 industrialized regions and have no chloromethane factories. However, there is
506 substantial chlor-alkali production in Hebei, Inner Mongolia and Xinjiang provinces
507 (Supplementary Fig. 11c). As chlor-alkali factories are regarded as potential sources for
508 CCl_4 emissions, possibly via chlorination of organic substances^{66,67}, they could also be
509 sources for CHCl_3 emissions as CHCl_3 is easily formed via haloform reactions during
510 chlorination¹⁶. The emissions in the seven sub-regions (Supplementary Fig. S8) are
511 strongly correlated ($r=0.74$) with caustic soda production in the regions⁴¹
512 (Supplementary Fig. S12), which further indicates a potential link between chlor-alkali
513 production and CHCl_3 emissions, although the exact process of CHCl_3 formation is
514 unclear.

515 **Discussion**

516 A substantial increase in the global CHCl_3 mole fractions and emissions up to 2015 had
517 previously been identified, and could have delayed the recovery of Antarctic
518 stratospheric ozone by up to 9 years if the increase continued (defined as the ‘continued

519 growth scenario' in Fang et al.⁹). The increase in both global CHCl₃ mole fractions and
520 emissions was found to continue until 2017, but both were then followed by a fall in
521 2018¹². The global emissions and mole fractions did not increase or decrease between
522 2019 and 2020, and the mole fractions in these years are similar to those in 2015 (Fig.
523 2-3). This implies that the impact of CHCl₃ on global ozone layer recovery may be
524 close to the 'constant mole fraction scenario' in the previous paper⁹. If the plateau in
525 mole fractions and emissions continues, the potential delay from CHCl₃ on Antarctic
526 stratospheric ozone recovery should be ~1 year, compared to the mole fraction baseline
527 in 1920⁹. Thus, a significant delay in the recovery of the ozone layer caused by the
528 increasing CHCl₃ emissions could be avoided if future CHCl₃ emissions do not increase.

529 The predicted future trajectory for CHCl₃ emissions is uncertain. The changes in global
530 CHCl₃ emissions have likely been dominated by emission changes from anthropogenic
531 sources in China between 2011 and 2020. By-product emissions during bleaching in
532 the pulp and paper industry, production leakage from the chloromethane industry and
533 emissions from solvent use in the pharmaceutical industry are recognized as important
534 sources of CHCl₃ emissions in China in our analyses. The year-to-year variations in
535 emissions from China and the differences between top-down and bottom-up emissions
536 may be reconciled by several uncertainties in anthropogenic emissions in the bottom-
537 up inventory, such as the lack of time-varying emissions factors for production leakage
538 and the pulp and paper industry, and the lack of quantification of emissions in the chlor-
539 alkali industry. However, the lack of available data limit further exploration of these
540 uncertainties. Further efforts, like carrying out high-frequency measurements in key

541 areas and samplings around important industries would offer a better understanding of
542 these uncertainties. Natural soil emissions are likely to be substantial in China (~32%),
543 as identified from the bottom-up inventory, and have potential interannual variations
544 related to the changes in annual temperature and precipitation. However, they are not
545 likely to be the main cause for the global emission changes considering the size of
546 China's land and global ocean emissions.

547 Most of the identified major anthropogenic sources of CHCl_3 in China can be controlled
548 effectively by measures such as applying chlorine-free bleach in the pulp and paper
549 industry or imposing stricter regulations on production leakage. These measures could
550 help maintain or reduce CHCl_3 emissions, to further mitigate the impacts of CHCl_3 on
551 the ozone layer. Even though the long-term impact on ozone layer recovery from CHCl_3
552 has been reduced due to the fall in emissions in recent years, its cumulative increased
553 emissions over 2011-2020 have already caused an integrated ozone depletion
554 comparable to that of increased CFC-11 emissions since 2012⁸, which have
555 subsequently decreased since 2018 (see Methods). Considering the increasing
556 importance of CHCl_3 for ozone depletion compared to ozone depleting substances
557 controlled under the Montreal Protocol, and that CHCl_3 emissions in East Asia can be
558 rapidly transported into the stratosphere, an improved understanding of its sources in
559 China is needed, to better understand the future evolution of stratospheric ozone.

560

561 **Data availability**

562 Measurement data of CHCl₃ from the Chinese network are provided in the
563 Supplementary Data file 1. Use of the Chinese measurement data in publications,
564 reports or presentations requires the users to contact B.Y. (yaobo@fudan.edu.cn) first
565 to discuss your interests.

566 **Code availability**

567 The code for the regional emission inversion framework is available at
568 <https://github.com/ACRG-Bristol/acrg> (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6834888>,
569 Rigby et al., 2022*), and all relevant inputs and outputs are available upon request from
570 M.A. (mindean@mit.edu). License to use NAME is available upon request to the UK
571 Met Office (enquiries@metoffice.gov.uk).

572 *Rigby, M. et al. ACRG-Bristol/acrg: ACRG v0.2.0 (v0.2.0), Zenodo [code],
573 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6834888>, 2022.

574 **Supporting Information**

575 Supplementary Information: Figures S1-S12 and Tables S1-S4 (PDF)

576 Supplementary Data 1: Raw observed CHCl₃ mole fractions from nine Chinese sites
577 used in the regional emission inversion framework (XLSX)

578 Supplementary Data 2: Derived top-down CHCl₃ emissions in China (XLSX)

579 Supplementary Data 3: Sectoral bottom-up CHCl₃ emission inventory in China (XLSX)

580 **Author Contributions**

581 M.A. designed the research. M.A. conducted the regional inverse modelling and
582 interpreted the results with the support of L.M.W., M.R. and A.L.G.. B.Y. provided
583 measurement data from the nine CMA sites and P.B.K., J.M., S.O'D., R.G.P., R.F.W.
584 and D.Y. provided global measurement data and calibrations. R.H. provided a priori
585 boundary condition values. M.A. led the writing of the manuscript, with contributions
586 from L.M.W., J.H., B.Y., M.R., J.M., A.L.G., R.G.P. and all other authors.

587 **Acknowledgements**

588 This work was supported by the National Key Research and Development Program of
589 China (Grant No. 2019YFC0214500) and Shanghai B&R Joint Laboratory Project (No.
590 22230750300). This work has benefited from the technical expertise of and the
591 assistance by the AGAGE (Advanced Global Atmospheric Gases Experiment) network
592 including the Medusa GC/MS system technology, calibrations of CHCl_3 measurements
593 and network operation, as well as Dr. Martin Vollmer from the Swiss Federal
594 Laboratories for Materials Science and Technology. Luke M. Western received funding
595 from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under
596 Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement no. 101030750. We acknowledge the support
597 from members of Atmospheric Chemistry Research Group at University of Bristol and
598 thank the U.K. Met Office for the support and licensing for NAME.

599 **Competing Interests**

600 The authors declare no competing interests.

601 **References**

- 602 (1) Engel, A.; Rigby, M. Chapter 1: Update on Ozone-Depleting Substances (ODSs)
603 and Other Gases of Interest to the Montreal Protocol. In *Scientific Assessment of*
604 *Ozone Depletion: 2018*; World Meteorological Organization, 2018; Vol. 58.
- 605 (2) Solomon, S.; Ivy, D. J.; Kinnison, D.; Mills, M. J.; Neely, R. R.; Schmidt, A.
606 Emergence of Healing in the Antarctic Ozone Layer. *Science* **2016**, *353* (6296),
607 269–274. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aae0061>.
- 608 (3) Oram, D. E.; Ashfold, M. J.; Laube, J. C.; Gooch, L. J.; Humphrey, S.; Sturges, W.
609 T.; Leedham-Elvidge, E.; Forster, G. L.; Harris, N. R. P.; Mead, M. I.; Samah, A.
610 A.; Phang, S. M.; Ou-Yang, C.-F.; Lin, N.-H.; Wang, J.-L.; Baker, A. K.;
611 Brenninkmeijer, C. A. M.; Sherry, D. A Growing Threat to the Ozone Layer from
612 Short-Lived Anthropogenic Chlorocarbons. *Atmos. Chem. Phys.* **2017**, *17* (19),
613 11929–11941. <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-17-11929-2017>.
- 614 (4) Hossaini, R.; Chipperfield, M. P.; Montzka, S. A.; Leeson, A. A.; Dhomse, S. S.;
615 Pyle, J. A. The Increasing Threat to Stratospheric Ozone from Dichloromethane.
616 *Nat. Commun.* **2017**, *8*, 15962. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms15962>.
- 617 (5) Randel, W. J.; Park, M.; Emmons, L.; Kinnison, D.; Bernath, P.; Walker, K. A.;
618 Boone, C.; Pumphrey, H. Asian Monsoon Transport of Pollution to the
619 Stratosphere. *Science* **2010**, *328* (5978), 611–613.
- 620 (6) Claxton, T.; Hossaini, R.; Wild, O.; Chipperfield, M. P.; Wilson, C. On the Regional
621 and Seasonal Ozone Depletion Potential of Chlorinated Very Short-lived
622 Substances. *Geophys. Res. Lett.* **2019**, *46* (10), 5489–5498.
623 <https://doi.org/10.1029/2018GL081455>.
- 624 (7) Ashfold, M. J.; Pyle, J. A.; Robinson, A. D.; Meneguz, E.; Nadzir, M. S. M.; Phang,
625 S. M.; Samah, A. A.; Ong, S.; Ung, H. E.; Peng, L. K.; Yong, S. E.; Harris, N. R.
626 P. Rapid Transport of East Asian Pollution to the Deep Tropics. *Atmos. Chem.*
627 *Phys.* **2015**, *15* (6), 3565–3573. <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-15-3565-2015>.
- 628 (8) Pyle, J. A.; Keeble, J.; Abraham, N. L.; Chipperfield, M. P.; Griffiths, P. T.
629 Integrated Ozone Depletion as a Metric for Ozone Recovery. *Nature* **2022**, *608*
630 (7924), 719–723. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-022-04968-8>.
- 631 (9) Fang, X.; Park, S.; Saito, T.; Tunnicliffe, R.; Ganesan, A. L.; Rigby, M.; Li, S.;
632 Yokouchi, Y.; Fraser, P. J.; Harth, C. M.; Krummel, P. B.; Mühle, J.; O’Doherty,
633 S.; Salameh, P. K.; Simmonds, P. G.; Weiss, R. F.; Young, D.; Lunt, M. F.;
634 Manning, A. J.; Gressent, A.; Prinn, R. G. Rapid Increase in Ozone-Depleting
635 Chloroform Emissions from China. *Nat. Geosci.* **2019**, *12* (2), 89–93.
636 <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41561-018-0278-2>.
- 637 (10) Dhomse, S. S.; Feng, W.; Montzka, S. A.; Hossaini, R.; Keeble, J.; Pyle, J. A.;
638 Daniel, J. S.; Chipperfield, M. P. Delay in Recovery of the Antarctic Ozone Hole

- 639 from Unexpected CFC-11 Emissions. *Nat. Commun.* **2019**, *10* (1), 5781.
640 <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-019-13717-x>.
- 641 (11) Fleming, E. L.; Newman, P. A.; Liang, Q.; Daniel, J. S. The Impact of Continuing
642 CFC-11 Emissions on Stratospheric Ozone. *J. Geophys. Res. Atmos.* **2020**, *125* (3).
643 <https://doi.org/10.1029/2019JD031849>.
- 644 (12) Laube, J. C.; Tegtmeier, S. Chapter 1: Update on Ozone-Depleting Substances
645 (ODSs) and Other Gases of Interest to the Montreal Protocol. In *Scientific*
646 *Assessment of Ozone Depletion: 2022*; World Meteorological Organization:
647 Geneva, Switzerland, 2022; Vol. 278.
- 648 (13) China Chlor-Alkali Industry Association (CCAIA). Report on Chloromethanes
649 Industry in China (in Chinese), 2021. <http://www.ccaon.com/jwllhw.asp>.
- 650 (14) Bie, P.; Fang, X.; Li, Z.; Wang, Z.; Hu, J. Emissions Estimates of Carbon
651 Tetrachloride for 1992–2014 in China. *Environ. Pollut.* **2017**, *224*, 670–678.
652 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2017.02.051>.
- 653 (15) Feng, Y.; Bie, P.; Wang, Z.; Wang, L.; Zhang, J. Bottom-up Anthropogenic
654 Dichloromethane Emission Estimates from China for the Period 2005–2016 and
655 Predictions of Future Emissions. *Atmos. Environ.* **2018**, *186*, 241–247.
656 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2018.05.039>.
- 657 (16) Aucott, M. L.; McCulloch, A.; Graedel, T. E.; Kleiman, G.; Midgley, P.; Li, Y.-F.
658 Anthropogenic Emissions of Trichloromethane (Chloroform, CHCl₃) and
659 Chlorodifluoromethane (HCFC-22): Reactive Chlorine Emissions Inventory. *J.*
660 *Geophys. Res. Atmos.* **1999**, *104* (D7), 8405–8415.
661 <https://doi.org/10.1029/1999jd900053>.
- 662 (17) McCulloch, A. Chloroform in the Environment: Occurrence, Sources, Sinks and
663 Effects. *Chemosphere* **2003**, *50* (10), 1291–1308.
- 664 (18) Cox, M. L.; Sturrock, G. A.; Fraser, P. J.; Siems, S. T.; Krummel, P. B.; O’Doherty,
665 S. Regional Sources of Methyl Chloride, Chloroform and Dichloromethane
666 Identified from AGAGE Observations at Cape Grim, Tasmania, 1998–2000. *J.*
667 *Atmos. Chem.* **2003**, *45* (1), 79–99.
- 668 (19) Trudinger, C. M.; Etheridge, D. M.; Sturrock, G. A.; Fraser, P. J.; Krummel, P. B.;
669 McCulloch, A. Atmospheric Histories of Halocarbons from Analysis of Antarctic
670 Firn Air: Methyl Bromide, Methyl Chloride, Chloroform, and Dichloromethane.
671 *J. Geophys. Res. Atmos.* **2004**, *109* (D22), D22310.
672 <https://doi.org/10.1029/2004jd004932>.
- 673 (20) Worton, D. R.; Sturges, W. T.; Schwander, J.; Mulvaney, R.; Barnola, J. M.;
674 Chappellaz, J. 20th Century Trends and Budget Implications of Chloroform and
675 Related Tri- and Dihalomethanes Inferred from Firn Air. *Atmos. Chem. Phys.* **2006**,
676 *6* (10), 2847–2863. <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-6-2847-2006>.
- 677 (21) An, M.; Western, L. M.; Say, D.; Chen, L.; Claxton, T.; Ganesan, A. L.; Hossaini,

- 678 R.; Krummel, P. B.; Manning, A. J.; Mühle, J.; O'Doherty, S.; Prinn, R. G.; Weiss,
679 R. F.; Young, D.; Hu, J.; Yao, B.; Rigby, M. Rapid Increase in Dichloromethane
680 Emissions from China Inferred through Atmospheric Observations. *Nat. Commun.*
681 **2021**, *12* (1), 7279. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-27592-y>.
- 682 (22) Zhang, G.; Yao, B.; Vollmer, M. K.; Montzka, S. A.; Mühle, J.; Weiss, R. F.;
683 O'Doherty, S.; Li, Y.; Fang, S.; Reimann, S. Ambient Mixing Ratios of
684 Atmospheric Halogenated Compounds at Five Background Stations in China.
685 *Atmos. Environ.* **2017**, *160*, 55–69.
686 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2017.04.017>.
- 687 (23) Yu, D.; Yao, B.; Lin, W.; Vollmer, M. K.; Ge, B.; Zhang, G.; Li, Y.; Xu, H.;
688 O'Doherty, S.; Chen, L.; Reimann, S. Atmospheric CH₃CCl₃ Observations in
689 China: Historical Trends and Implications. *Atmos. Res.* **2020**, *231*, 104658.
690 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosres.2019.104658>.
- 691 (24) Arnold, T.; Mühle, J.; Salameh, P. K.; Harth, C. M.; Ivy, D. J.; Weiss, R. F.
692 Automated Measurement of Nitrogen Trifluoride in Ambient Air. *Anal. Chem.*
693 **2012**, *84* (11), 4798–4804. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ac300373e>.
- 694 (25) Miller, B. R.; Weiss, R. F.; Salameh, P. K.; Tanhua, T.; Grealley, B. R.; Mühle, J.;
695 Simmonds, P. G. Medusa: A Sample Preconcentration and GC/MS Detector
696 System for in Situ Measurements of Atmospheric Trace Halocarbons,
697 Hydrocarbons, and Sulfur Compounds. *Anal. Chem.* **2008**, *80* (5), 1536–1545.
698 <https://doi.org/10.1021/ac702084k>.
- 699 (26) Vollmer, M. K.; Zhou, L. X.; Grealley, B. R.; Henne, S.; Yao, B.; Reimann, S.;
700 Stordal, F.; Cunnold, D. M.; Zhang, X. C.; Maione, M.; Zhang, F.; Huang, J.;
701 Simmonds, P. G. Emissions of Ozone-Depleting Halocarbons from China.
702 *Geophys. Res. Lett.* **2009**, *36* (15), L15823.
703 <https://doi.org/10.1029/2009GL038659>.
- 704 (27) Prinn, R. G.; Weiss, R. F.; Arduini, J.; Arnold, T.; DeWitt, H. L.; Fraser, P. J.;
705 Ganesan, A. L.; Gasore, J.; Harth, C. M.; Hermansen, O.; Kim, J.; Krummel, P. B.;
706 Li, S.; Loh, Z. M.; Lunder, C. R.; Maione, M.; Manning, A. J.; Miller, B. R.;
707 Mitrevski, B.; Mühle, J.; O'Doherty, S.; Park, S.; Reimann, S.; Rigby, M.; Saito,
708 T.; Salameh, P. K.; Schmidt, R.; Simmonds, P. G.; Steele, L. P.; Vollmer, M. K.;
709 Wang, R. H.; Yao, B.; Yokouchi, Y.; Young, D.; Zhou, L. History of Chemically
710 and Radiatively Important Atmospheric Gases from the Advanced Global
711 Atmospheric Gases Experiment (AGAGE). *Earth Syst. Sci. Data* **2018**, *10* (2),
712 985–1018. <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-10-985-2018>.
- 713 (28) Jones, A.; Thomson, D.; Hort, M.; Devenish, B. The U.K. Met Office's Next-
714 Generation Atmospheric Dispersion Model, NAME III. In *Air Pollution Modeling*
715 *and Its Application XVII*; Borrego, C., Norman, A.-L., Eds.; Springer US, Boston,
716 MA: Boston, MA, 2007; pp 580–589.
- 717 (29) Say, D.; Kuyper, B.; Western, L.; Khan, M. A. H.; Lesch, T.; Labuschagne, C.;

- 718 Martin, D.; Young, D.; Manning, A. J.; O’Doherty, S.; Rigby, M.; Krummel, P. B.;
719 Davies-Coleman, M. T.; Ganesan, A. L.; Shallcross, D. E. Emissions and Marine
720 Boundary Layer Concentrations of Unregulated Chlorocarbons Measured at Cape
721 Point, South Africa. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* **2020**, *54* (17), 10514–10523.
722 <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.0c02057>.
- 723 (30) Walters, D.; Baran, A. J.; Boutle, I.; Brooks, M.; Earnshaw, P.; Edwards, J.;
724 Furtado, K.; Hill, P.; Lock, A.; Manners, J.; Morcrette, C.; Mulcahy, J.; Sanchez,
725 C.; Smith, C.; Stratton, R.; Tennant, W.; Tomassini, L.; Van Weverberg, K.; Vosper,
726 S.; Willett, M.; Browse, J.; Bushell, A.; Carslaw, K.; Dalvi, M.; Essery, R.; Gedney,
727 N.; Hardiman, S.; Johnson, B.; Johnson, C.; Jones, A.; Jones, C.; Mann, G.; Milton,
728 S.; Rumbold, H.; Sellar, A.; Ujiie, M.; Whittall, M.; Williams, K.; Zerroukat, M.
729 The Met Office Unified Model Global Atmosphere 7.0/7.1 and JULES Global
730 Land 7.0 Configurations. *Geosci. Model Dev.* **2019**, *12* (5), 1909–1963.
731 <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-12-1909-2019>.
- 732 (31) Lunt, M. F.; Rigby, M.; Ganesan, A. L.; Manning, A. J. Estimation of Trace Gas
733 Fluxes with Objectively Determined Basis Functions Using Reversible-Jump
734 Markov Chain Monte Carlo. *Geosci. Model Dev.* **2016**, *9* (9), 3213–3229.
735 <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-9-3213-2016>.
- 736 (32) Ganesan, A. L.; Rigby, M.; Zammit-Mangion, A.; Manning, A. J.; Prinn, R. G.;
737 Fraser, P. J.; Harth, C. M.; Kim, K.-R.; Krummel, P. B.; Li, S.; Mühle, J.;
738 O’Doherty, S. J.; Park, S.; Salameh, P. K.; Steele, L. P.; Weiss, R. F.
739 Characterization of Uncertainties in Atmospheric Trace Gas Inversions Using
740 Hierarchical Bayesian Methods. *Atmos. Chem. Phys.* **2014**, *14* (8), 3855–3864.
741 <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-14-3855-2014>.
- 742 (33) Hoffman, M. D.; Gelman, A. The No-U-Turn Sampler: Adaptively Setting Path
743 Lengths in Hamiltonian Monte Carlo. *J. Mach. Learn. Res.* **2014**, *15*, 1593–1623.
- 744 (34) Neal, R. M. Slice Sampling. *Ann. Stat.* **2003**, *31* (3), 705–767.
745 <https://doi.org/10.1214/aos/1056562461>.
- 746 (35) Monks, S. A.; Arnold, S. R.; Hollaway, M. J.; Pope, R. J.; Wilson, C.; Feng, W.;
747 Emmerson, K. M.; Kerridge, B. J.; Latter, B. L.; Miles, G. M.; Siddans, R.;
748 Chipperfield, M. P. The TOMCAT Global Chemical Transport Model v1.6:
749 Description of Chemical Mechanism and Model Evaluation. *Geosci. Model Dev.*
750 **2017**, *10* (8), 3025–3057. <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-10-3025-2017>.
- 751 (36) General Administration of Customs of China. *China Customs Statistical Yearbook*
752 *(in Chinese)*; China Customs Press, Beijing, China: Beijing, China, 2020.
- 753 (37) Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC). *Good Practice Guidance*
754 *and Uncertainty Management in National Greenhouse Gas Inventories*; IPCC,
755 Japan: Japan, 2000.
- 756 (38) Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC). *2019 Refinement to the 2006*
757 *IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories*; IPCC, Switzerland:

- 758 Switzerland, 2019.
- 759 (39) Zhao, X.-C.; Xiang, X.-Y.; Wang, S.-C.; Jiang, P.-N.; Gao, D.; Yi, L.-Y.; An, M.-
760 D.; Bai, F.-L.; Xu, W.-G.; Zhang, J.-J.; Hu, J.-X. By-Production, Emissions and
761 Abatement Cost–Climate Benefit of HFC-23 in China’s HCFC-22 Plants. *Adv.*
762 *Clim. Change Res.* **2023**, S1674927823000126.
763 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.accre.2023.01.003>.
- 764 (40) United States Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA). Locating and
765 Estimating Air Emissions from Sources of Chloroform, 1984.
766 <https://www.epa.gov/sites/default/files/2020-11/documents/chloroform.pdf>
767 (accessed 2022-12-29).
- 768 (41) National Bureau of Statistics of China. *China Statistical Yearbook*; China
769 Statistics Press, Beijing, China: Beijing, China, 2021.
- 770 (42) Ministry of Housing and Urban-Rural Development of China. *China Urban-Rural*
771 *Construction Statistical Yearbook (in Chinese)*; China Statistics Press, Beijing,
772 China: Beijing, China, 2020.
- 773 (43) Lobert, J. M.; Keene, W. C.; Logan, J. A.; Yevich, R. Global Chlorine Emissions
774 from Biomass Burning: Reactive Chlorine Emissions Inventory. *J. Geophys. Res.*
775 *Atmos.* **1999**, *104* (D7), 8373–8389. <https://doi.org/10.1029/1998jd100077>.
- 776 (44) Wu, J.; Kong, S.; Wu, F.; Cheng, Y.; Zheng, S.; Qin, S.; Liu, X.; Yan, Q.; Zheng,
777 H.; Zheng, M.; Yan, Y.; Liu, D.; Ding, S.; Zhao, D.; Shen, G.; Zhao, T.; Qi, S. The
778 Moving of High Emission for Biomass Burning in China: View from Multi-Year
779 Emission Estimation and Human-Driven Forces. *Environ. Int.* **2020**, *142*, 105812.
780 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2020.105812>.
- 781 (45) Department of Energy Statistics, National Bureau of Statistics. *China Energy*
782 *Statistical Yearbook (in Chinese)*; China Statistics Press, Beijing, China: Beijing,
783 China, 2021.
- 784 (46) United States Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA). *WebFIRE database*.
785 <https://www.epa.gov/electronic-reporting-air-emissions/webfire> (accessed 2022-
786 02-25).
- 787 (47) Liu, Y.; Lu, W.; Dastyar, W.; Liu, Y.; Guo, H.; Fu, X.; Li, H.; Meng, R.; Zhao, M.;
788 Wang, H. Fugitive Halocarbon Emissions from Working Face of Municipal Solid
789 Waste Landfills in China. *Waste Manag.* **2017**, *70*, 149–157.
790 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2017.08.042>.
- 791 (48) Crippa, M.; Guizzardi, D.; Muntean, M.; Schaaf, E.; Lo Vullo, E.; Solazzo, E.;
792 Monforti-Ferrario, F.; Olivier, J.; Vignati, E. *EDGAR v7.0 Greenhouse Gas*
793 *Emissions*. https://edgar.jrc.ec.europa.eu/dataset_ghg70 (accessed 2022-12-25).
- 794 (49) Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. *FAOSTAT Greenhouse*
795 *Gas Emissions Database*. <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/GT> (accessed
796 2022-12-25).

- 797 (50) Chang, J.; Peng, S.; Yin, Y.; Ciaia, P.; Havlik, P.; Herrero, M. The Key Role of
798 Production Efficiency Changes in Livestock Methane Emission Mitigation. *AGU*
799 *Adv.* **2021**, 2 (2), e2021AV000391. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2021AV000391>.
- 800 (51) Dimmer, C. H.; Simmonds, P. G.; Nickless, G.; Bassford, M. R. Biogenic Fluxes
801 of Halomethanes from Irish Peatland Ecosystems. *Atmos. Environ.* **2001**, 35 (2),
802 321–330.
- 803 (52) Laturnus, F.; Haselmann, K. F.; Borch, T.; Grøn, C. Terrestrial Natural Sources of
804 Trichloromethane (Chloroform, CHCl₃)—an Overview. *Biogeochemistry* **2002**, 60
805 (2), 121–139.
- 806 (53) Khalil, M. A. K.; Rasmussen, R. A.; Shearer, M. J.; Chen, Z.-L.; Yao, H.; Yang, J.
807 Emissions of Methane, Nitrous Oxide, and Other Trace Gases from Rice Fields in
808 China. *J. Geophys. Res. Atmos.* **1998**, 103 (D19), 25241–25250.
809 <https://doi.org/10.1029/98JD01114>.
- 810 (54) Khalil, M.; Moore, R.; Harper, D.; Lobert, J.; Erickson, D.; Koropalov, V.; Sturges,
811 W.; Keene, W. Natural Emissions of Chlorine-containing Gases: Reactive
812 Chlorine Emissions Inventory. *J. Geophys. Res. Atmos.* **1999**, 104 (D7), 8333–
813 8346.
- 814 (55) Li, S.; Kim, J.; Kim, K. R.; Muhle, J.; Kim, S. K.; Park, M. K.; Stohl, A.; Kang,
815 D. J.; Arnold, T.; Harth, C. M.; Salameh, P. K.; Weiss, R. F. Emissions of
816 Halogenated Compounds in East Asia Determined from Measurements at Jeju
817 Island, Korea. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* **2011**, 45 (13), 5668–5675.
818 <https://doi.org/10.1021/es104124k>.
- 819 (56) Wang, C.; Shao, M.; Huang, D.; Lu, S.; Zeng, L.; Hu, M.; Zhang, Q. Estimating
820 Halocarbon Emissions Using Measured Ratio Relative to Tracers in China. *Atmos.*
821 *Environ.* **2014**, 89, 816–826. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2014.03.025>.
- 822 (57) Kim, J.; Li, S.; Kim, K.-R.; Stohl, A.; Mühle, J.; Kim, S.-K.; Park, M.-K.; Kang,
823 D.-J.; Lee, G.; Harth, C. M.; Salameh, P. K.; Weiss, R. F. Regional Atmospheric
824 Emissions Determined from Measurements at Jeju Island, Korea: Halogenated
825 Compounds from China. *Geophys. Res. Lett.* **2010**, 37 (12), L12801.
826 <https://doi.org/10.1029/2010gl043263>.
- 827 (58) Wen, Z.; Di, J.; Zhang, X. Uncertainty Analysis of Primary Water Pollutant
828 Control in China's Pulp and Paper Industry. *J. Environ. Manage.* **2016**, 169, 67–
829 77. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2015.11.061>.
- 830 (59) Zhang, C.; Chen, J.; Wen, Z. Alternative Policy Assessment for Water Pollution
831 Control in China's Pulp and Paper Industry. *Resour. Conserv. Recycl.* **2012**, 66,
832 15–26. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2012.06.004>.
- 833 (60) People's Government of Shandong Province. Action Plan for Comprehensive
834 Control of Air Pollution in the Autumn and Winter of 2017-2018 in the Beijing-
835 Tianjin-Hebei Region and Its Surrounding Areas (in Chinese), 2017.

- 836 http://www.shandong.gov.cn/art/2017/9/27/art_2259_26171.html.
- 837 (61) The State Council of People's Republic of China. Air Pollution Prevention and
838 Control Action Plan (in Chinese), 2013.
839 http://www.gov.cn/zhengce/content/2013-09/13/content_4561.htm.
- 840 (62) China Meteorological Administration. *China Climate Bulletin (in Chinese)*; 2021.
- 841 (63) Rhew, R. C.; Teh, Y. A.; Abel, T.; Atwood, A.; Mazéas, O. Chloroform Emissions
842 from the Alaskan Arctic Tundra. *Geophys. Res. Lett.* **2008**, *35* (21), L21811.
- 843 (64) Khalil, M. A. K.; Rasmussen, R. A.; French, J. R. J.; Holt, J. A. The Influence of
844 Termites on Atmospheric Trace Gases: CH₄, CO₂, CHCl₃, N₂O, CO, H₂, and Light
845 Hydrocarbons. *J. Geophys. Res.* **1990**, *95* (D4), 3619.
846 <https://doi.org/10.1029/JD095iD04p03619>.
- 847 (65) United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP). Report on Emission
848 Reductions and Phase-out of CTC (Decision 55/45), 2009.
849 UNEP/OzL.Pro/ExCom/58/50.
- 850 (66) Sherry, D.; McCulloch, A.; Liang, Q.; Reimann, S.; Newman, P. A. Current
851 Sources of Carbon Tetrachloride (CCl₄) in Our Atmosphere. *Environ. Res. Lett.*
852 **2018**, *13* (2), 024004. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/aa9c87>.
- 853 (67) Hu, L.; Montzka, S. A.; Miller, B. R.; Andrews, A. E.; Miller, J. B.; Lehman, S. J.;
854 Sweeney, C.; Miller, S. M.; Thoning, K.; Siso, C.; Atlas, E. L.; Blake, D. R.; de
855 Gouw, J.; Gilman, J. B.; Dutton, G.; Elkins, J. W.; Hall, B.; Chen, H.; Fischer, M.
856 L.; Mountain, M. E.; Nehrkorn, T.; Biraud, S. C.; Moore, F. L.; Tans, P. Continued
857 Emissions of Carbon Tetrachloride from the United States Nearly Two Decades
858 after Its Phaseout for Dispersive Uses. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* **2016**, *113* (11), 2880–
859 2885. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1522284113>.
- 860

861 **Synopsis:** A recent increase and subsequent decrease in emissions of ozone-depleting
862 chloroform is inferred in China using atmospheric measurements.

863

864 **TOC:**

865